

Ibero-American higher education institutions facing Covid-19

The article aims to identify the variables associated with the perception that the members of the educational community (professors and students) from higher education institutions in Ibero-America during, the first weeks of the Covid-19 pandemic. The study based on an Internet applied survey from April 6th to 20th of 2020, with 771 respondents ($1-\alpha=95\%$ and $e=3,5$) from Argentina, Colombia, Chile, Spain, Mexico, and Puerto Rico. The main results reveal how the positive assessment of higher institutions depends on how professors and students perceived the risk of infection and other external variables (non-institutional) such as their previous experience in virtual environments. To a lesser degree, during the study period, professors and students with the most negative states of mind expressed more significant difficulties in managing academic activities. Therefore, it recommends that higher education institutions in Ibero-American work improve communication channels and implement programs of accompaniment that foster resiliency, starting from the construction of institutional bonds and strengthening the socioemotional skills of both professors and students.

Keywords: higher education, perceptions, social support, students, professors, COVID-19

Introduction

In 2020, on a global scale comparable to a disaster situation has been lived due to COVID-19, which has caused an immediate negative impact on people's lives, according to Turcaz, Pascual and Ibarra (2016), and Valdez, Borrayo and Munoz (2018). In this context, higher education institutions have had to assume their formative mission, from a perspective of their responsibility, outreach, and contribution to social welfare, within the before mentioned scenario, addressing the prevention of negative consequences that are caused by disasters such as the one experienced, according to studies conducted by Perez et al. (2019) and Astudillo and Sandoval (2019). An issue that requires, from higher education institutions, the active and critical involvement of professors, students and administrative staff (Akareem and Hossain, 2016; Dicker et al. 2019), as well as those who lead them to prove mechanisms that ensure support and cooperation between the different actors involved in these programs. This may impact the perception of efficacy and quality of higher education institutions by its educational

agents, as highlighted by Seyfried and Pohlenz (2018). They posit that the assessment that makes institutional quality is influenced by having a good quality perception of the management and decision making of these institutions of higher education. The before mentioned has a positive effect on the quality of life and state of mind of those involved in higher education contexts, under adverse circumstances like the ones that have experienced due to Covid-19 (Mohammadi and Karupiah, 2019; Zapa, Navarro and Rendón, 2017).

The perception of social and institutional support from higher education institutions in times of Covid-19 in 2020 is relevant, especially demands greater understanding from an educational perspective from the scholarly community (professors, students, and staff) to develop a bond with the organizations. Relations that can be strengthened or weakened, depending on the sense of support that each one of them has a relationship that is emphasized by Blanco-Portela et al. (2018) or Lipka, Forkosh and Meer (2019). These bonds built from emotional or generated bonds can permit the exercise of academic tasks under their care. This process contributes to foster a sensation of normality between those are an active part of higher educations institution (for example professors, students, and staff), despite the state of alert or situation of confinement that has tended to be experienced, since the beginning of 2020; as well as the sensation of being able to aid other members of the community that are at higher risk.

The skills, knowledge, and adaptability of the members of an organization allows them to mobilize resources and respond to disasters, with or without the aid of established organizations, and has been defined as social capital or community resilience (Toscana and Fernandez, 2017), and apply in the setting of the sanitary crisis experienced in 2020. What motivates people and groups into action, not just to ride out a situation that has personal or family impact, but to transversely mobilize resources and aid responses (Alvarado et al., 2019). During this process, the perception of risk and the stress generated by the sensation of vulnerability, that is perceived individually or collectively, according to Sandoval et al. (2017), can be assumed to be triggers for the resilience shown in three scenarios: keeping up a positive lifestyle despite the events that increase risk; searching for balance given the environmental circumstances, and developing immediate recovery upon a momentary imbalance due to stressful phenomena.

In this regard, Chaparro, Carreño and Arias (2019) group the perception of social support that individuals and groups can demonstrate in situations of risk and vulnerability upon a disaster into categories: those that can mitigate the sense of vulnerability that impacts upon an individual (support that lightens the load, confronting and overcoming to deal with the situation, the need for emotional support, the need for tangible support); the ones that strengthen their place as social actors (providing support for others, information and communication technologies as mechanisms); perception of state and institutional support; and finally, being visible and supported.

[FIGURE 1 HERE]

The global challenge resulting from the emergence of COVID-19 has no precedent (PAHO/WHO). Every scope of social and individual life suffers its repercussions, and educational systems have found themselves in the compelling need to transform traditional educational models, and implement others that are of a blended or online nature, with a demand for the use of technology and emerging instructional practices (Garcia-Ruiz and Perez-Escoda 2020; Mancero et al., 2020). The state of seclusion experienced by many world citizens, including Ibero-American countries, as a measure against the spread of the virus, brought with it the closure of institutions of higher education, upon an imminent risk of infection. A fact that forced many higher education institutions with a strong presence in the traditional face to face educational models was shifting gears, transferring the classroom and workspace to home environments, which were used by many citizens to both work and study. A situation that, in the case of Ibero American countries, may have resulted in becoming a more significant problem than that experienced by developed countries, given the connectivity problems and the wide digital gap that, even before Covid-19, existed amongst many segments of the population (Pardo and Cobo, 2020).

The sanitary crisis scenario lived since the first trimester of 2020 has added a new dimension to the challenges faced by the parties involved in higher education: strengthening the institutional framework that fosters the accomplishment of activities under the responsibility of professors and students, as well as advancing the research and extension required (Garcia, 2020), but also actions regarding pedagogy, technology,

and connectivity (Pardo and Cobo, 2020). Also achieves flexibility in academic activity, without that involving an increase in socio-educational gaps which were already existent before the pandemic; but also, the review of communication processes (Instituto de Investigaciones sobre la Universidad y la Educacion, IISUE, 2020), and the accompaniment that higher education institutions must provide to their members to ensure the fulfillment of educational goals. Something that accomplishes without setting aside the promotion of a psychosocial framework favors the reduction of the perceived risk and stress caused by the vulnerability recognized due to the Covid-19 pandemic (Gendron, 2017; Escobar, 2020; Extremera, 2020).

If higher education institutions successfully handle the scenario resulting from the Covid-19 sanitary crisis, there will be increased individual and collective resiliency, at a social level, from the so-called 'new normal' driven by the media and public and private players; and has aided in reflecting the emerging social scenario. In this context, the IISUE (2020) proposes a series of questions that higher education institutions have to address as multiple challenges:

... How to provide educational continuity to matters which displaced the classroom to the home and will once more return to the school? How to blend educational events with social and individual health challenges? How to build political and institutional responses that are differentiated and relevant? How to prepare citizens to effectively deal with the risk and multiple situations of calamity that may arise? (p. 16).

The present study contributes to the knowledge base. It provides some answers to these questions, without setting aside the main stakeholders: their educational centers are providing university professors and students, who have their perceptions about the roles they play within institutional frameworks, the risks, vulnerability and the value given to their identity, their sense of belonging and the feeling of support which they feel.

Materials and method

The present study has the goal of identifying the variables associated with the perception that members of the educational community (professors and students) had of the academic situation of higher education institutions in Ibero-America during the first

weeks of confinement caused by Covid-19. This work based on a survey that was applied online with probability sampling from April 6th to 24th of 2020 and made up of 771 sampling units ($1-\alpha=95\%$ y $e=3,5$). This period coincides with the first weeks of official confinement declared by the Ibero-American countries that address in the present study: Argentina (March 24th, 2020), Colombia (March 24th, 2020), Chile (March 19th, 2020), Spain (March 14th, 2020), Mexico (March 24th, 2020), and Puerto Rico (March 19th, 2020).

The selection of analyzed countries took into consideration the country of origin of the higher education institutions represented by professors ($n=251$) and students ($n=520$) that answered the online survey disseminated by the authors of the present work. The sociodemographic profile of the participants of this study characterized by being overwhelmingly female, of young adult age (between 25 and 39 years of age), and spending confinement in the company of someone, and they had already experienced many weeks of isolation in their countries of residence. Regarding the academic profile of the study sample, a more significant proportion of the academic community members were associated with private higher education institutions (5.5 of each ten survey respondents) and exercised their academic duties (as professors or students) mainly in undergraduate in person. settings.

[TABLE 1 HERE]

To address the proposed subject, they ask to point out the institutional areas they had direct contact with during the study period and highlight a variation in their institutional perception compared to the one they held before Covid-19. This last feature was the one taken into account when contrasting with other independent variables collected directly through questions that explicitly referred to it, and others created through questions posed in the survey, which allowed the study of features related to, for example rating the level of the perceived academic barriers, their level of perception of social and state of mind support, the sensation of the level of risk to Covid-19, rating the level of information and communications equipment available at home, level of satisfaction with social relations and conditions of space for home academic activity, as well as the level of exercise or development of guidelines for the development of healthy habits during

confinement. In addition to other variables directly related to academic activity, such as the educational method practiced before isolation, the educational level where academic duties exercise, and the average number of daily hours devoted to academic activities, before and during confinement, amongst others.

The data gathered from the survey was the subject of an internal study of internal validity regarding some of the leading independent variables created from the questions posed to survey respondents (see table 2). The α observed in most of these variables (State of mind¹, Academic Space², and Academic Barriers³) turned out to be acceptable if we take into consideration what is mentioned by Nunnally (1978) and Loewenthal (1996). While, in the case of other variables (Social support perception⁴, and Healthy guidelines or habits during confinement⁵), the observed α can consider being sufficient. Especially if the exploratory nature of this work is to consider (Nunnally, 1978) or the heterogeneity of the topics addressed in the indicators that conform to it (Magnunsson, 1978).

[TABLE 2 HERE]

¹ The State of Mind variable built from the sum of options given by the survey respondents regarding questions related to feelings of nervousness, worry, ability to control problems, level of irritability, fear, or depression that they could have been feeling during the confinement period. This variable was categorized in range (through a Likert 5-point scale, with one being very positive and five being very negative) from the sum of the set of answers given to all questions considered mentioned.

² The Academic Space variable made up of issues like the size of the space, organization of this workspace, soundproofing to other areas cohabitated during confinement, lighting, humidity, ventilation, and air quality, among others which group under a new variable categorized through a 5 point Likert scale (1 being very low and five being very high).

³ The Academic Barriers variable was made up of questions, assessed in a dichotomous way (0 and 1), that aimed to measure the presence or not of situations that hampered academic responsibilities during confinement, like for example constant interruptions by children, the number of domestic tasks under their obligation, the difficulty in keeping the schedule established for these activities, and the experienced lack of concentration, among other measured traits. The sum of the results of all these questions was useful for the creation of a new variable with a Likert 5 point scale, where 1 was a very little presence of academic barriers, and 5 was a high presence of obstacles, during the fulfilment of the educational activities under the responsibility of those surveyed.

⁴ The Perception of social support variable measured on a 3 point Likert scale (always, sometimes, never), as a result of the sum of the answers given by survey-takers to questions associated to the number of times they had experienced feelings of sadness, loneliness, happiness, as well as having felt loved, among other aspects that take into consideration. Following the scenario posed to each survey taker, the scale's rating order rotated to correctly create the variable considered in addressing this subject in the present article.

⁵ The healthy guidelines variable is the result of the sum of the answers given by the survey takers to questions related to the following of routines, talking with friends and family, doing physical activity, having a healthy and varied diet, and undertaking hobbies, among others. The sum of the answers given grouped under Likert 5 options (with 1 being no day and 5 Almost every day)

The SPSS Statistics 20 program used to process and analyze the data collected through the applied online survey.

Results

At the moment of estimating the level of institutional contact, it is essential to see how during the analyzed period, in general terms, most of the members of the surveyed academic community (76% of the 771 survey respondents) did not give any indication of having had direct contact, while working during confinement, with any of the academic or administrative areas of their institutions. The result is notable if we consider the nature of the social exception the survey takers lived through during the period of information collection. Among those who did have contact with institutional areas during this period, 6.5 of each 10 had direct contact with two or more institutional areas. Among those who only had direct contact with one area, almost 70% of them had contact with departments related to administrative or technical fields. The data shows us what would be considered by the authors of the present work as a low institutional contact scenario, if the social framework lived during the first weeks of confinement is taken into account, with the undertaking of social distancing measures defining and having an impact on daily work at the study centers to which each of the survey takers linked. Above all, if the perception that study participants had about the experienced academic anxiety during the weeks of confinement, they lived through is taken into account, the mean ($\bar{x}$) of the rating obtained by the sampling in that variable was of 5.83/10 maximum points. A value that would have an observed standard deviation that is high ($\sigma=2,897$), which would give an account of the dispersion of the collected answers around our study variable, and the asymmetrical distribution form of the obtained results. Thinking this would seem logical, if the novel social context that was being lived socially during the first weeks of confinement considered, being characterized by questions about what and how to proceed in the face of Covid-19, which measures were effective for it, and until when the social distancing applied by the totality of analyzed countries would cease, despite some of them (the case of Mexico) trying to avoid these kinds of measures initially.

Despite what presented in the previous paragraph, it points out that the mean institutional assessment for the analyzed period was positive⁶ ($\bar{x}=3.94/5$ points and $\sigma=0.914$). A period with a variation of almost three points above the evaluation that they had, in general terms, of these entities before confinement, considering the level of survey takers that expressed having had a change in the way they perceived the institutions to which they were linked, as students or professors, in Ibero-America (Table 3).

[TABLE 3 HERE]

From a psycho-social perspective, the data allows us to establish features that characterize those surveyed in the present work. The mean ($\bar{x}$) of the data provided by them will enable them to see that there is:

- A medium level of accomplishing or meeting healthy guidelines or habits ($\bar{x}=3.52/5$ points and $\sigma=0.645$);
- Low perception of risk ($\bar{x}=1.59/3$ points and $\sigma=0,511$) in light of Covid-19, in general terms;
- A common understanding of social support during confinement ($\bar{x}=1.92/3$ points and $\sigma=0,279$);
- A medium-low emotional state ($\bar{x}=2.88/5$ points and $\sigma=0.876$); and
- A medium-level satisfaction that they expressed having with social relations during the analyzed period ($\bar{x}=3.25/5$ points and $\sigma=1.130$)

It is vital to underscore, from the data presented in the last paragraph, that the levels of dispersion observed in the state of mind and the satisfaction with social relations ($\sigma=0.876$ and $\sigma=1.130$), would give an account of high variability in the answers provided by those surveyed. The result helps to see a very volatile psycho-social

⁶ The academic area was the one that had the best assessment by survey takers, with a mean score of 4/5 points, followed by the administrative area (3.98/5 points) and the institutional leadership area (3.57/5 points)

context, in both aspects. What comes expected in a context of considerable uncertainty, anxiety, and social and individual stress experienced during the analyzed period.

From the socio-educational point of view, the data allows us to see a context that could be considered positive (despite the dispersion in the answers given by those surveyed). Particularly, if we take into consideration the levels of the answers provided by study participants, regarding:

- Academic barriers at home (for example lack concentration, lack of motivation, excess work, need to adapt to teleworking, caring for and interruptions coming from children in their care, and housework under their responsibility), presented by participants in the study ($\bar{x}=1,76/5$ puntos y $\sigma=0,878$);
- The quality of the spaces used to undertake the academic work under their responsibility ($\bar{x}=3.98/5$ points and $\sigma=0,869$); and
- The assessment gives concerning the performance of the tech equipment (information and communications technologies) arranged to carry out their responsibilities ($\bar{x}=3.95/5$ points and $\sigma=1,029$).

A context that can be better understood if we take into account the tech capacity in their homes during confinement expressed by the survey takers, where we can notice in most the availability of the hardware necessary to give continuity to their academic responsibilities. A scenario in which 8 of every ten said that they owned laptop or desktop computers and smartphones, but only 4 out of every 10 have fiber optic access (more than 30 MB). An aspect that could hinder or limit access to content through digital resources requires much bandwidth, for example.

The data collected also allows a better understanding of the valuation level given to digital resources (for example institutional email account, exam manager, virtual subject platforms, videoconferencing channels, and institutional digital repositories) made available by higher education institutions, when undertaking academic duties, in the framework of the confinement experienced by the survey takers. A context in which 7 of each ten survey takers said they considered these resources very good or excellent, while 2 of each ten survey takers gave an average rating (neither positive nor negative) and only one of 10 survey takers rated negatively. Even when their use was not intensive, considering that 8 out of every ten survey takers said that they used them only

sometimes, and only two said that they used them intensively during the analyzed state of confinement.

The data extracted and analyzed in the present work allows us to establish the possible associations in the observed variation in the level of the rating given by members of the surveyed academic community (professors and students) of higher education institutions in Ibero-America, regarding the independent variables observed in the present work. In the first place, a moderately significant association can be found between the institutional rating given during confinement and the level of anxiety linked to fulfilling academic activities under the responsibility of those surveyed ($T_c = -.290$, $p = .000$, $n = 384$). Thus, when survey takers had higher levels of stress, the institutional rating was less (negative).

Table 4 also allows seeing a set of variables associated with the variability, either positive or negative, of the rating given by the members of the surveyed academic community, within the level of the higher education institutions of Ibero-American countries.

[INSERT TABLE 4]

The data shown in table 4 lets you view how the variables with a moderately significant degree of association to the institutional rating given during confinement is the one that refers to the score given to the digital resources made available by the higher education institutions of which the survey takers were part of during confinement. Mainly, in what refers to teaching, exercises, testing, debate, and institutional communication between peers or other members of the community, the survey takers were part. The institutions' technical resources focus on virtual learning platforms, support for the development of online exams, messaging and communication services, and access to existing digital repositories. The association observed around this variable backed by the institutional ability to provide resources fitting to being able to face, in most cases according to the responses of survey takers, a framework of transformation of the main form of education in their respective centers of higher education (in-person training) to a remote format supported by information and communications technologies. The result is pertinent in a moment when digital turned

out to be the only option taken into consideration to give continuity to the academic work of professors and students, during the analyzed period.

Table 4 also allows the identification of a series of psycho-social variables that had an impact on the perception of the members of the studied academic community. Such is the case of the knowledge of Covid-19 risk, also with a moderate association. Those who had a greater understanding of risk to this virus were those who had a more positive institutional rating. The degree of significance observed in this variable is similar to the one found in the state of mind variable (Table 4), meaning, those who said they had a positively favorable mood, beside the situation of confinement, were those whom better rate the institution to which they were academically associated. Other variables that turn out to be relevant can also observe from the data presented in Table 4 when taking into account the variation in perception experienced by professors and students associated with the higher education institutions in Ibero-America. Such is the case of the opinion that they said they had of aspects related to mood, satisfaction with the social relations that they had or expressed in their answers, the level of compliance with healthy life guidelines, atmosphere, as well as the barriers and academic space that occurred to them during the undertaking of their educational activities from home. The values for the Kendall Tau-C and the levels of significance observed in Table 4, regarding the rating of the institution, allow to state that those who met a high or very high healthy life guideline had a positive state of mind and a favorable rating of social relations, despite the confinement that they were living, presented very few barriers and considered that they had adequate spaces at home for the development of the academic duties under their responsibility, being the ones who better rated the Ibero-American higher education institutions of which they were part.

Suppose a comparison of medians made between the independent variable (institutional rating) and the set of independent variables considered in this work. In that case, a considerable difference between the medians of institutional-grade stated by survey takers and the institutions' public or private character can observe through the Mann-Whitney U test ($z=26770.50$, $p=.000$). Hence, public institutions had a lower rating ($\bar{x}=0.67$ and $\sigma=6.396$) in comparison to those with academic duties in private institutions ($\bar{x}=5.06$ and $\sigma=5.230$). Conversely, the Kruskal-Wallis test ($H(2)=26.595$, $p=.000$) also allows the observance of variation in the mean institutional rating, about the educational level where survey responders undertake their academic activity (Table

5). Therefore, academic activities at a postgraduate level ($\bar{x}=5.16$ and $\sigma=5.811$), had a better rating, compared to undergraduate ($\bar{x}=1.99$ and $\sigma=6.139$) or doctoral degree ($\bar{x}=4$ and $\sigma=6,459$).

[INSERT TABLE 5]

The Mann-Whitney U test ($z=18200$, $p=.000$) shows how those who were in institutions based on an in-person education model before confinement had a rating that, even though favorable, was much lower ($\bar{x}=2.10$ and $\sigma=6.369$) than in the case of those who were at educational entities that already had a hybrid or online model ($\bar{x}=5.51$ y $\sigma=4.896$).

It is also important to note, through the comparison of medians, allow to recognize, a relation between the level of joint responsibility in domestic chores and the institutional rating given by survey-takers ($H(2)=15.489$, $p=.000$). In Table 6, a difference in rating levels can observe in all of the categories that make up this variable versus institutional rating. Thus, the possibility of improvement in the distribution of domestic chores, by professors and students associated with the studied Ibero-American higher education institutions, had a more favorable rating ($\bar{x}=4.13/5$ points and $\sigma=5.982$), in comparison who have not seen variations in these tasks ($\bar{x}=2.08/5$ points and $\sigma=6,288$) or have worsened their situation in their respective homes ($\bar{x}=1.59/5$ points and $\sigma=6.090$).

[INSERT TABLE 6]

The data collected also shows a context that would merit consideration from higher education institutions in Ibero-America. The level of institutional perception is linked to the number of weeks of confinement experienced by the members of the academic community that make up the institution (Table7), worsens as the time of isolation experienced by those surveyed increases ($H(4)=55.456$, $p=.000$).

[INSERT TABLE 7]

Finally, the increase in the number of hours devoted to academic work during confinement was another aspect where a relationship to institutional rating can be observed, on the part of professors and students surveyed for the present work ($H(2)=14.361$, $p=.001$). The median found among those that pointed out a lower number of work hours were the ones that had a better institutional rating, compared to those who had more work hours (Table 8).

[INSERT TABLE 8]

Discussion and Conclusions

This study focuses on the situation that lived during the first months of the present year 2020, the so-called COVID-19 pandemic. Confinement measures were put in place to control infections in almost all countries of the world. This reality impacted all scopes of life, as was underscored by PAHO/WHO (2020) and affected higher education institutions. In this context, there was a desire to know the academic performance of higher education institutions, drawing from professors' perception and rating, and students who make their lives in those institutions. In an exploratory way, all done by addressing a myriad of socio-educational and psycho-social variables related to the sanitary crisis gave rise to the confinement experienced worldwide, including the analyzed Ibero-American countries. A scenario in which, at least during the first weeks that frame this research, professors, and students did not have the contact that would come expected with the higher education institutions.

This data allows the stressing of the importance of improving communication channels in higher education institutions, the capacity of the digital resources made available for the development of academic activities, tending to the home technological capacity of their professors and students, and programs of accompaniment to these. The reality would favor a greater resilience, by the construction of institutional bonds, the strengthening of socio-emotional skills, and better access to educational content and spaces. At least in the terms presented in the introduction, following what was exhibited

by Gendron (2017), Blanco-Portela et al. (2018), Dicker et al. (2019), Lipka, Forkosh and Meer (2019) or Extremera (2020). Especially if it considers that, except the association observed between institutional rating and the digital resources made available by the higher education institutions, the rest were determined by psycho-social and socio-educational variables that do not depend directly from the management of the higher education institutions, but from the socio-sanitary, the domestic and technological reality of each of the members of the studied population.

All measures that push the strengthening of the resilience of the academic actors will turn out to be useful in ensuring the active and critical role that must be assumed by students, at the moment of confronting pedagogical continuity, the harmonization of education to current and future sanitary challenges, and the increase of the ability to respond to these types of situations, from political and institutional actions that are differentiated and pertinent. Something that will help improve the social support perception of their members and the incubation of an institutional framework that contributes to the advancement of learning, research, and extension goals of these kinds of entities (Garcia, 2020). Notably, by answering to a revision of the pedagogical, technological and connectivity issues that today turn out to be critical considerations in favoring academic flexibility, as is well pointed out by Pardo and Cobo (2020), under a society that is defined by the current pandemic, and with a high risk of widening the socio-educational gaps already existing in the analyzed countries (Ibero-America).

It is crucial to take into consideration what has been presented up to this moment if we assume that, despite a positive institutional perception from the surveyed professors and students, it marked by dispersion and volatility in the opinions expressed by the 771 survey-takers (following the standard deviation observed in this matter).

So far commented, leads to raising that unless the institutions advance in three recommendations: communication, techno-pedagogical support, and social or socio-emotional support, there will be a higher risk of having a worse perception of the effectiveness and quality provided by them. The association observed between institutional attitude and state of mind, and the rest of the highlighted variables studied in the present article for the studied population take into account. This reality demands, from social institutions like higher education institutions, to advance mechanisms that help in diminishing the feeling of vulnerability that has marked the current social scenario in the face of Covid-19 (Escobar, 2020), and that answer to the categories of

perception of social support under events of this type, as presented by Chaparro, Carreño and Arias (2019).

Despite the exploratory character of the study and the need to advance in studies of this nature, that help to understand better the impact of Covid-19 in the perception of higher education institutions by their members, the previously outlined conclusions turn out to be maybe even more relevant if we address the median comparison made in this article. The data leads to consider in a more pressing form all that highlight if compared with the type of institution (public or private) and following the predominating educational model (in person or hybrid or online). Something that had an even more negative impact in the institutional assessment when those surveyed practiced their academic work at an undergraduate level and mostly exercised an in-person educational model and belonged to public higher education institutions. Not surprisingly, if the standards of maturity between undergraduate and postgraduate and doctorate students consider the emerging educational format could help the latter to face the analyzed period in a more autonomous and resilient way. These aspects match what was stated by authors Akareem and Hossain (2016), Seyfried and Pohlenz (2018), Mohammadi and Karupiah, (2019), at the moment of emphasizing that private higher education institutions tend to have better infrastructure (technological) conditions than public institutions, and in the same way, there can be an understanding of the differences between those surveyed that were associated to educational institutions based on hybrid or online models, since they exhibited a lower transformation in the way they undertook the academic duties under their responsibility during the period of study.

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